

Studies on some Coumaradione Condensations

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Condensation of several *o*-phenylenediamines with some coumaran-2,3-diones have been carried out. Elemental analysis, infra-red and mass spectrum studies remove ambiguities in the existing literature and indicate that the condensation products have quinoxaline structure of the type (VI).

FRIES¹ had condensed coumaran-2,3-diones with *ortho*-phenylenediamine in the hope of obtaining coumarophenazines (I). Actually however he had obtained dihydroxy derivatives of the type (II). These structures obviously arise by the opening of the furan ring and the following mechanism may be suggested :

The same products were also obtained by the condensation of *o*-hydroxyphenylglyoxylic acid (III) with the diamines. Staudinger and co-workers² have later prepared similar products. Giua and Francis³ have also studied the condensation of 4,5- and 6,7-benzocoumarandione with *ortho*-phenylenediamine and claimed to have obtained the related coumarophenazine. Chatterjea⁴, however, had shown that these compounds could also be obtained from the related glyoxylic acids and the products obtained by Giua and co-worker were in reality of the type (II), although there was a discrepancy of melting point in one case. The quinoxaline structures were supported by elemental analysis.

It was, therefore, considered interesting to condense a number of *o*-phenylenediamines with some coumarandiones, in an attempt to investigate upon the contentions.

For the present study, nine *o*-phenylenediamines namely 3-chloro-, 3-bromo-, 3-iodo-,⁵ 4-methoxy-, 4-methyl-, 4,5-dimethyl-, 4,5-dichloro-, 4,6-dibromo- and 4-nitro-*o*-phenylenediamines have been condensed with coumarandione, and its 5-methyl- and

6-methoxy- derivatives, by boiling acetic acid solutions of the two for a few minutes. Separation of solids took place readily except with methyl coumarandione which generally needed a little longer heating. The condensation may lead to the production of isomers. It has, however, been found that one product is mainly produced which has been isolated

purified and studied. In the case of condensation of 6-methoxycoumarandione and 3-chloro-*o*-phenylenediamine two products in equal amounts have been obtained having the structure (IV) or (V) although exact structural assignment was not undertaken.

The infra-red spectra of these two compounds are different and the elemental analysis is the same as expected.

The yield of the crude products and other details have been recorded in the table. The compounds are all of attractive shades of yellow to orange-brown.

All the condensation products are soluble in alkali, indicating their phenolic nature. The spectra taken

TABLE

Sl. No.	Reactants*	Mol. Formula	Yield (%)	Appearance (Solvent of crystn.)	M.P. (°C) of major product	Analysis	
						Found	Reqd.
1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	
1.	C+3-chloro-P	C ₁₄ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₂	79	Bright yellow needles (Ethanol)	265	C, 61.2 H, 3.6 N, 10.0	C, 61.7 H, 3.3 N, 10.3
2.	5-Methyl-C+3-chloro-P	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₂	69	Orange yellow needles (Pyridine)	317-18	C, 61.5 H, 3.8 N, 10.3	C, 62.8 H, 3.8 N, 9.8
3.	6-Methoxy-C+3-chloro-P	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₃	63 ⁺	(i) Orange yellow needles (ii) Orange brown needles (Pyridine + nitrobenzene + chloroform)	272-75 314-18	C, 58.9 H, 3.6 N, 9.3	C, 59.5 H, 3.6 N, 9.3
4.	C+3-iodo-P	C ₁₄ H ₉ IN ₂ O ₂	75	Deep yellow needles (Nitrobenzene)	378-80	C, 46.3 H, 2.2 N, 7.5	C, 46.1 H, 2.5 N, 7.7
5.	C+4-methoxy-P	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃	49	Reddish orange granules (Nitrobenzene + benzene)	308-309	N, 10.2	N, 10.4
6.	5-Methyl-C+4-methoxy-P	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃	89	Dull reddish orange granules (Pyridine + nitrobenzene)	285-89	N, 10.0	N, 9.9
7.	6-Methoxy-C+4-methoxy-P	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	67	Deep yellow granules (Pyridine)	240-41	C, 63.9 H, 4.5 N, 9.8	C, 64.4 H, 4.7 N, 9.4
8.	C+4-methyl-P	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	75	Deep yellow needles (Ethanol)	260-62	C, 71.0 H, 4.5 N, 11.0	C, 71.4 H, 4.8 N, 11.1
9.	5-Methyl-C+4-methyl-P	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	70	Deep yellow needles (Ethanol + ethyl acetate)	275-77	N, 10.8	N, 10.5
10.	6-Methoxy-C+4-methyl-P	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃	80	Deep yellow needles (Ethanol)	243-46	N, 10.1	N, 9.9
11.	C+4,5-dimethyl-P	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	64	Shining yellow needles (Acetic acid)	312-13	C, 71.6 H, 5.6 N, 10.7	C, 72.2 H, 5.3 N, 10.5
12.	5-Methyl-C+4,5-dimethyl-P	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	72	Orange flakes (Nitrobenzene)	339-41	C, 72.6 H, 6.1 N, 10.2	C, 72.9 H, 5.7 N, 10.0
13.	6-Methoxy-C+4,5-dimethyl-P	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃	85	Deep yellow needles (Pyridine)	291-92	C, 68.7 H, 5.7 N, 9.6	C, 68.9 H, 5.4 N, 9.5
14.	C+4,5-dichloro-P	C ₁₄ H ₈ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂	90	Dull yellow granules (Acetic acid)	312-15	C, 54.2 H, 2.9 N, 9.0	C, 54.7 H, 2.6 N, 9.1
15.	5-Methyl-C+4,5-dichloro-P	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂	65	Deep orange needles (Pyridine + nitrobenzene)	339-40	C, 55.8 H, 3.7 N, 8.6	C, 56.1 H, 3.1 N, 8.7
16.	6-Methoxy-C+4,5-dichloro-P	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₃	89	Shining orange flakes (Pyridine)	338-40(d)	C, 53.1 H, 3.5 N, 8.6	C, 53.4 H, 3.0 N, 8.3
17.	C+4,6-dibromo-P	C ₁₄ H ₈ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂	66	Yellow flakes (Nitrobenzene)	299-303	N, 7.0	N, 7.1
18.	5-Methyl-C+4,6-dibromo-P	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂	78	Amber yellow granules (Pyridine)	328-30	C, 43.6 H, 2.4 N, 6.8	C, 43.9 H, 2.4 N, 6.8

+ C = Coumaran-2,3-dione; P = *ortho*-Phenylenediamine.

+ Total yield of two isomers.

TABLE—Contd.

Sl. No.	Reactants ⁺	Mol. Formula	Yield (%)	Appearance (Solvent of crystn.)	M.P. (°C) of major product	Analysis	
						Found	Reqd.
1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	
19.	6-Methoxy-C+ 4,6-dibromo-P	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₃	42	Orange flakes (Nitrobenzene)	317-18	C, 41.8 H, 2.6 N, 7.0	C, 42.3 H, 2.3 N, 6.6
20.	C+3-bromo-P	C ₁₄ H ₉ BrN ₂ O ₂	77	Yellow needles (Acetic acid+ethanol)	286-88	C, 52.9 H, 2.9 N, 9.0	C, 53.0 H, 2.8 N, 8.8
21	C+4-nitro-P	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ O ₄	61	Amber brown granules (Pyridine-nitrobenzene)	298-302	C, 59.0 H, 3.0 N, 14.9	C, 59.4 H, 3.2 N, 14.8
22.	5-Methyl-C+4-nitro-P	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₄	68	Orange red needles (Pyridine+nitrobenzene)	291-301	C, 60.5 H, 4.1 N, 14.2	C, 60.6 H, 3.7 N, 14.1
23.	6-Methoxy-C+ 4-nitro-P	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₅	79	Bright reddish brown flakes (Pyridine+nitrobenzene)	330-40(d)	N, 13.3	N, 13.4

on KBr pellets, however, did not reveal the presence of hydroxyl group (which if present might be shrouded by the moisture in KBr). Distinct hydroxyl absorption in the region of 3500 to 3600 cm⁻¹ is however noticeable in spectra taken in carbon tetrachloride phase. The frequency shift is ascribed to hydrogen bonding⁶ and the weak absorption to poor solubility of the compounds in this solvent. All the same the existence of -NH group is indicated in all the compounds by the presence of a weak band at 3280 cm⁻¹. All the compounds, moreover, show an intense carbonyl absorption in the range 1660 to 1668 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of a -CO-NH group. Therefore the compounds are probably existing in the lactum form (VI) which is doubtlessly stabilised by hydrogen bonding as indicated above.

(VI)

Experimental

The following general procedure was adopted :

To a hot solution of the coumarandione in acetic acid, was added a solution of the diamine in warm acetic acid and the mixture was refluxed for a short time to ensure complete reaction. The precipitated

product was filtered out and crystallised several times to get pure product.

The mass spectrum of one of the compounds (serial No. 20) of the Table was recorded. The peaks *m/e* with their relative intensities in parenthesis are given below :

317(100), 315(100), 300(10·1), 298(11·2), 289(100), 287(100), 274(4·2), 272(1·3), 261(100), 259(99·6), 249(5·0), 247(6·4), 238(9·0), 237(12·7), 236(22·9), 234(20·3), 224(0·6), 222(1·3).

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